

Topology optimization with arbitrarily many materials: density versus level-set applied to a hybrid excited rotor

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This work addresses the topology optimization of a rotor of a hybrid-flux machine. The main challenge is handling many different material types (non-linear magnetic steel, air, DC conductors, and magnets with several orientations). Classical gradient-free topology optimization approaches are inapplicable due to the high dimensionality of the optimization space, and usual density-based methods fail to provide meaningful results by falling into uninteresting local optima. Therefore, two general and distinct methodologies are proposed: an extended density approach and a level-set method based on the topological derivative. Both methods result in meaningful designs that are analyzed and discussed, and recommendations are formulated.

Index Terms—Hybrid excited machine, Multi-material topology optimization, Density method, Level-set, Topological derivative

I. INTRODUCTION

HYBRID-FLUX electrical machines aim to combine the high energy density of permanent magnets with the controllability of wound field synchronous machines, making them suitable for electromotive applications [1]. Their design is generally carried out by standard parametric optimization, limited to the initial topology chosen by the designer. Topology optimization can be performed to overcome this limitation. Although many different structures are available [2], making hybrid-excited machines an ideal playground for topology optimization algorithms, the literature on topology optimization of hybrid-flux machines is scarce. For one of the few available studies, we refer to [3], where a 2-step approach consisting of combinatorial optimization and local search is used. The design problem is indeed challenging due to the comparatively high number and distinct nature of materials involved (steel, air, permanent magnets with different magnetization directions, back-and-forth DC conductors). Therefore, this paper aims to apply one-step multi-material topology optimization algorithms to design a hybrid-excited rotor without initial geometry information. After presenting the optimization problem, extensions of the density method and a level-set approach based on topological derivatives are compared.

II. OPTIMIZATION PROBLEM

This paper focuses on a hybrid-excited radial-flux rotor, containing permanent magnets (PM) with 12 different orientations and back-and-forth DC conductors for excitation, as well as non-linear ferromagnetic material and air. Typical expectations from a hybrid-excited machine are:

- high torque at low speed, where the positive DC excitation strengthens the magnetic flux produced by the magnets;
- low flux at high speed to avoid excessive back-EMF, so the negative DC excitation weakens the magnets' flux.

Our goal is to optimize the material distribution Ω within the 2D cross-section of a single hybrid excited rotor pole D_r , surrounded by D_{ext} , such that the objective function

$$f : \Omega \mapsto \min \{ \phi^+(\Omega) + \phi^-(\Omega), \phi^+(\Omega) - \phi^-(\Omega) \} \quad (1)$$

is maximized. Here, ϕ^+ and ϕ^- are the outer fluxes (measured between point x_1 and x_2 in Fig. 1) when the excitation current is positive and negative, respectively. Therefore, two magnetostatic simulations are performed to evaluate ϕ^+ and ϕ^- , the current density in the excitation coil being $J_{DC} = \pm 10 \text{ A/mm}^2$. Since we want the optimization as general as possible, the stator is replaced with air in D_{ext} to avoid potential unwanted slot effects. The objective function is chosen to promote high ϕ^+ together with a low amplitude of ϕ^- as shown in Fig. 2. In particular, a design with only PM or only coil excitation leads to $\phi^+ = \phi^-$ or $\phi^+ = -\phi^-$, respectively, both corresponding to $f = 0$. We consider a total of $N = 16$ candidate materials: non-linear magnetic steel, air, forth-and-back DC conductors as well as PM with 12 different magnetization directions from 0° to 330° .

Fig. 1: Simulation setup (radiuses are in mm)

Fig. 2: Contour plot of f

III. MULTI-MATERIAL TOPOLOGY OPTIMIZATIONS

In this section, we use two different advanced multi-material topology optimization methodologies. The results are compared with a more usual density method on a Cartesian

interpolation domain. The performances are listed in Table I, and the maximum number of iterations is set to 500.

A. Density method on a Cartesian domain

We introduce a density function $\rho : D_r \rightarrow \mathcal{D} \subset \mathbb{R}^p$ which assigns to each point of the rotor a point in the material domain \mathcal{D} . Here, we consider a hypercube $\mathcal{D} = [-1, 1]^4$ represented in Fig. 3a, as it would usually be done in the literature. Each of the 16 vertices of \mathcal{D} is associated with a candidate material, and points inside \mathcal{D} correspond to "gray materials" that are non-physical mixtures. Then, an unconstrained gradient-based algorithm is performed on f . The obviously suboptimal results of this naive optimization approach are depicted in Fig. 4a.

B. Extended density approach

Clearly, the choices of \mathcal{D} and material assignment to its vertices play an important role in the optimization, and the Cartesian structure of \mathcal{D} is a limitation [4]. To separate the different natures of materials, a hierarchical interpolation on custom polytopes is employed [5] and depicted in Fig. 3b, handled by a projected gradient algorithm. The result is shown in Fig. 4b and exhibits a parallel flux structure. However, the choice of the interpolation domain requires expertise, and some gray materials remain.

C. Topological derivative approach

To avoid these issues, we also investigate a level set approach based on the topological derivative, i.e., the sensitivity of a domain-dependent cost function with respect to a topological perturbation of the domain. A systematic way of computing topological derivatives for nonlinear magnetostatic problems is given in [6]; when dealing with nonlinear materials, offline precomputations are needed. The material space $\mathcal{D} = \mathbb{R}^{N-1}$ is now divided into N sectors selected from the values of $N-1$ level-set functions [7]. A representation of \mathcal{D} is given in Fig. 3c for $N=3$ for convenience; in the present study we have $N=16$. We obtain the design presented in Fig. 4c, similar to the designs obtained with the hierarchical density approach with even better performances.

Fig. 3: Optimization spaces associated with each point $x \in D_r$.

Fig. 4: Resulting designs after topology optimization.

TABLE I: Optimization results with method (a) density on hypercube, (b) density on hierarchical domain, (c) level-set based on topological derivative.

Method	Iterations	ϕ^+ (Wb/m)	ϕ^- (Wb/m)	f (Wb/m)
(a)	450	1.09×10^{-2}	7.08×10^{-4}	1.02×10^{-2}
(b)	150	1.29×10^{-2}	5.58×10^{-4}	1.24×10^{-2}
(c)	120	1.43×10^{-2}	7.55×10^{-6}	1.43×10^{-2}

IV. CONCLUSION

This work presents two advanced multi-material topology optimization methodologies, which have been applied to the design of a hybrid-excited rotor. Both approaches succeed in finding meaningful parallel hybrid excited structures [1], contrary to the usual density method on a Cartesian domain. Some improvements can still be made. The extended density approach requires an expert choice of the interpolation domain and may lead to intermediate materials in the optimized design, while the level-set approach based on topological derivatives returns crisp interfaces but requires precomputation regarding the material behavior. In the full paper, a thorough comparison of the considered methods and obtained designs will be made.

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